

Competencies of School of Health Science Professions laboratory teachers using Hyflex Platform as an innovative learning technique: A basis for faculty development program

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Abstract

A teacher plays a very significant and vital role in knowledge or learning formation and dissemination; thus, a student will find learning more rewarding if he finds his teacher is competent and the teaching is very effective. The study assessed the competencies of laboratory teachers from the School of Health Science Professions using the Hyflex platform as an innovative learning technique for students. The research made use of descriptive research, and by using a self-made questionnaire, these were statistically computed using specific tools such as frequency and percentage, weighted mean, t-test, and chi-square test. Based on the salient findings of this study, the School of Health Science Professions' laboratory teachers are young and dominated with males. The study revealed that the teachers are competent in the areas of planning and teaching materials, instructional strategies, communication skills, and evaluation tools using the Hyflex platform. There is a significant difference in the perceptions of the students and teachers themselves in their competencies. There is a significant relationship between the competencies of the teachers and their years of experience in the teaching profession and forms of training attended. A seminar training course could help the laboratory teachers to improve their competencies and skills.

Keywords: Competencies; Hyflex platform; Health science professions; Laboratory teachers; Faculty development program.

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Introduction

The teacher plays a very significant and vital role in knowledge or learning formation and dissemination; thus, a student will find learning more rewarding if he finds his teacher is competent and the teaching is very effective. One or more skills whose mastery could influence its attainment, as well as a connection to all three categories under which that performance can be evaluated—knowledge, skills, and attitudes—are a few indicators of competency (Mandal, 2018). As well as being measured and observable, competencies may also be evaluated. The proper method of giving information, application, and skills to learners is referred to as teacher competency (Kagoda, 2016). It encompasses both process and content knowledge. Therefore, it may be said that competencies are the information, abilities, and values that are necessary for a competency-based education (Gervais, 2016).

Teaching is an extremely challenging profession, especially in the health sciences, which are regarded to be very demanding areas (Shernoff et al., 2017). No other subject teacher must deal with such numerous scenarios, a theoretically challenging subject, and a group of students who bring different preconceptions and previous knowledge to the classroom (Wellington & Ireson, 2017). Indeed, it entails lots of effort and time for learning to occur, both for the teacher and the student. Future successful science professionals depend largely on how well laboratory teachers have trained and taught them. There is an immense need for competent teachers who teach and train students for quality education and, consequently, to be better people when they soon become professionals.

The study assessed the competencies of laboratory teachers from the School of Health Science Professions using the Hyflex platform as an innovative learning technique for students. Moreover, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the laboratory teachers as to:
 - a. Age
 - b. Gender
 - c. Civil Status
 - d. Highest Educational Attainment
 - e. Professional Eligibility
 - f. Number of Years in the Teaching Profession
 - g. Training Attended by the Respondents
 - h. Forms of Training
 - i. Level of Trainings Attended?
2. What is the level of competence of the laboratory teachers as perceived by themselves and the students?
3. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the students and the laboratory teachers in their competencies?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of competencies of the laboratory teachers to the following variables?
5. What faculty development program can be proposed to improve the competencies of laboratory teachers?

Methodology

To learn more about the current state of the study's subject, descriptive research was employed. Using the Hyflex platform, it describes, records, analyzes, and interprets the current situation regarding the skills of fifteen (15) laboratory teachers from the School of Health Science Professions (SHSP). Using a questionnaire checklist, it also provides descriptive details on each respondent's personal profile. Additionally, de Ocampo-Acero and Leuterio (2006) stated that descriptive research focuses on actual situations, relationships, or emerging trends. A questionnaire was the primary instrument used by the researchers to gather data. However, an unstructured interview was used to support the data.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

To determine the profile variables of the SHSP laboratory teachers as to age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, professional eligibility, and years of experience in the teaching profession and training, **frequency and percentage** were used. To determine the competencies of the SHSP laboratory teachers as perceived by themselves and the students in terms of planning and teaching materials, instructional strategies, communication skills, and evaluation tools, **weighted means** were used.

To find if there is any significant difference between the perceptions of the students and the SHSP laboratory teachers themselves in their competencies, **t-test** was used. **Chi-square** was used to determine

if there is any significant relationship between the level of competencies of the SHSP laboratory teachers and their profile variables, such as highest educational attainment, professional eligibility, years of experience in the teaching profession, and training attended.

Results and Discussion

1. What is the profile of the laboratory teachers?

Table 1. Profile of the laboratory teachers according to age

Age	Frequency	Percent
20-30	10	66.7
31 above	5	33.3
Total	15	100

Presented in Table 1 is the profile of the respondents according to age. The data show that out of 15 laboratory teachers, 10, or 66.7 percent, have ages ranging from 20-29, while 33.3 percent, or five respondents, have ages ranging from 30-39. The data revealed that most laboratory teachers in the School of Health Science Professions are young and in the age range of 20–30.

Table 2. Profile of the laboratory teachers according to gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	13	86.7
Female	2	13.3
Total	15	100

Table 2 shows the profile of the laboratory teachers according to gender. The data showed that out of 15 respondents, the majority, or 86.7 percent, are males, while 13.3 percent are females. The result indicates that teaching indeed is not only a female-dominated profession as we are used to. Nowadays, we already have more male teachers in the academe, as evidenced in the table.

Table 3. Profile of the laboratory teachers according to civil status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percent
Single	13	86.7
Married	2	13.3
Total	15	100

Table 3 determines the profile of the laboratory teachers according to civil status. The majority (13 or 86.7 percent) of the laboratory teachers are single, while two (2) or 13.3 percent are married. The result indicates that most of the laboratory teachers who opted to face the challenges of teaching are single.

Table 4. Profile of the laboratory teachers according to their highest educational attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	1	6.7
Bachelor's Degree with MA/MS units	11	73.3
Master's Degree with EdD/PhD units	3	20.0
Total	15	100

Table 4 presents the profile of the respondents according to the highest educational attainment. It can be gleaned from the table that most laboratory teachers are bachelor's degree holders with Master of Arts (MA) or Master of Science (MS) units with a frequency of 11, or 73.3 percent, while 3, or 20.0 percent, are master's degree holders with Doctor of Education (EdD) or Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), and only one

(1), or 6.7 percent, holds a bachelor’s degree. The large number of bachelor’s degree holders with MA/MS units among the laboratory teachers indicated that they apparently give priority concern to their professional growth and advancement through the pursuit of further graduate studies (Wendler et al., 2012).

Table 5. Profile of the respondents according to professional eligibility

Professional Eligibility	Frequency	Percent
Licensure Examination	15	100
None	0	0
Total	15	100

The professional eligibility profile of the laboratory teachers is shown in Table 5. All (15 or 100 percent) of the laboratory teachers are licensure examination passers. As gleaned from the table, it only means that the institution is strict in terms of the qualification of their laboratory instructors.

Table 6. Profile of the respondents according to number of years in teaching profession

Years in Teaching	Frequency	Percent
1 year – 5 years	12	80.0
6 years – 10 years	2	13.3
Above 10 years	1	6.7
Total	15	100

The number of years of the respondents in the teaching profession is presented in Table 6. The data shows that 12, or 80 percent, have experience as a laboratory teacher for one to five years. There are two (2) or 13.3 percent who have experiences for 6 to 10 years and one (1) or 6.7 percent for above 10 years. The data revealed that most of the laboratory teachers are not that long in the teaching profession. This affirmed that most of them are young teachers. Moreover, it is also indicated that there are only a few teachers who manage to teach laboratory subjects for a long period of time.

Table 7. Profile of the respondents as to having any training

Having Job Training Along Job Assignment	Frequency	Percent
Yes	15	100
No	0	0
Total	15	100

Presented in Table 7 is the profile of the respondents according to the training attended along with their job assignments. As gleaned from the table, all the respondents have training along with their job assignments (15 respondents or 100 percent). The data indicated that all the laboratory teachers are aware that training is very significant in the professional growth and development of teachers. Thus, data shows that the school administrators give opportunities to their faculty members to attend training along with their job assignments. Related studies affirm that one of the factors that contribute to the competency of teachers is the attendance of seminars, conventions, or training (Ahmed et al., 2021; Ganal et al., 2019; Mannila et al., 2018).

Table 8. Profile of the respondents as to the form of training

Form of Training	Frequency	Percent	Rank
Seminar	13	86.7	1
Conference	9	60.0	3
Workshop	7	46.7	4
Specific Area	10	66.7	2

Table 8 shows the profile of the respondents as to the form of training attended. These would help them enhance their knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The data from the above table reveals that seminars (13 or 86.7 percent) ranked first among those forms of training attended by the laboratory teachers. Training in a specific area (10 or 66.7 percent) ranked second, followed by conference (9 or 60 percent) and workshop (7 or 46.7 percent), respectively.

The table revealed that the laboratory teachers have attended seminars to further enhance their knowledge, skills, and attitudes towards teaching science. As an adage goes, “*You cannot give what you do not have.*” Professionals’ desire to advance their knowledge, abilities, and skills is an essential part (Collin et al., 2012). It is expected of laboratory teachers to do this. They must generate and take advantage of every chance to advance their expertise. Through training such as seminars, conferences, and workshops, they will be encouraged to learn from others as well as from how they teach their techniques (Trust et al., 2016).

Table 9. Profile of the respondents as to the level of training

Level of Training	Frequency	Percent	Rank
International	1	6.7	8
National	9	60.0	2
Regional	6	40.0	5
Division	8	53.3	3
District	5	33.3	6
School	10	66.7	1
Local/Provincial Government Unit	2	13.3	7
Private Agency Sponsored	7	46.7	4

Table 9 presents the profile of the respondents as to the level of training attended. As gleaned from the table, training at the school level (10 or 66.7 percent) ranked first, followed by the national level (9 or 60 percent); division level (8 or 53.3 percent); private agency-sponsored (7 or 46.7 percent); regional level (6 or 40 percent); district level (5 or 33.3 percent); local/provincial government unit level (2 or 13.3 percent); and national level (1 or 6.7 percent), respectively.

The data revealed that most of the laboratory teachers attended training conducted at the school level, although many of them also attended training given at the national level. The data also show that opportunities for training given at an international level are very limited, and not everybody is given the chance to attend it (Datnow & Hubbard, 2016). Nonetheless, laboratory teachers have attended training at least once, although at different levels.

2. What is the level of competence of the laboratory teachers as perceived by themselves and the students?

Table 10. Level of Competencies of the Laboratory Teachers as Perceived by Themselves and the Students

Area	Laboratory Teachers			Students		
	Weighted Mean	SD	Descriptive Value	Weighted Mean	SD	Descriptive Value
Planning and Teaching Materials	4.21	0.04	Competent	3.88	0.04	Competent
Instructional Strategies	4.15		Competent	3.91		Competent
Communication Skills	4.25		Competent	3.94		Competent
Evaluation Tools	4.16		Competent	3.83		Competent
Overall Weighted Mean	4.19		Competent	3.89		Competent

The data from Table 10 show that both the laboratory teachers and the students are affirming that the teachers are competent in the areas of planning and teaching materials, instructional strategies, communication skills, and evaluation tools. Furthermore, the table also reveals that among the given areas, both respondents confirmed that competency in communication skills has the highest rate.

3. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the students and the laboratory teachers in their competencies?

Table 11. Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Students and the Laboratory Teachers in their Competencies

Variable	Weighted Mean	SD	t-comp	Significance
Laboratory Teachers	4.19	0.04	10.71	Significant
Students	3.89	0.04		

Note: 0.05 level of significance

Table 11 presents the significant difference between the perception of the respondents in the competencies of laboratory teachers. The data revealed that the laboratory teachers’ perception has an overall weighted mean of 4.19 with a standard deviation of 0.04, while students’ perception has an overall weighted mean of 3.89 with a standard deviation of 0.04.

In testing whether there is a significant difference between the perception of the students and the laboratory teachers in their competencies, a t-test was used. A computed value of 10.71 at the 0.05 level of significance, which is greater than the tabular value of 1.943, indicates the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the laboratory teachers’ competencies as perceived by the students. Moreover, it was indicated that although both respondents affirmed the laboratory teachers as competent, there is still a significant difference in their perceptions.

4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of competencies of the laboratory teachers to the following variables?

Table 12. Chi-square Analysis on the Level of Competencies of Laboratory Teachers when Grouped According to Profile Variables

Variable Compared	Chi-square Value	Degree of Freedom	Critical Value	Verbal Interpretation
Highest Educational Attainment	2.51	4	9.35	Not Significant
Professional Eligibility	5.24	6	12.59	Not Significant
Years of Experience in the Teaching Profession	16.39	8	15.50	Significant
Form of Training	13.57	6	12.59	Significant
Level of Training	6.07	14	23.68	Not Significant

Table 12 presents the chi-square value of the profile variables compared, such as highest educational attainment, professional eligibility, years of experience in the teaching profession, and training. The data denoted that among the given profile variables, years of experience in the teaching profession and form of training show significant results. This implies that the laboratory teachers can become competent as they stay longer in the teaching profession and as they attend training that help them in their professional growth and development.

5. What faculty development program can be proposed to improve the competencies of laboratory teachers?

Proposed Seminar Training on “Teaching Laboratory Course On-line”

Objectives:

Generally, the seminar training aims to improve the competencies of the Laboratory teachers. Specifically, it aims to:

1. inspire and motivate laboratory teachers, leading them towards the acceptance of enhancement needed to become more competent especially with the integration of virtual platforms in the laboratory.
2. help them enhance further their knowledge, skills, and attitudes in teaching laboratory course.
3. employ the obtained knowledge, skills, and attitudes in teaching laboratory.

Expected Output: Highly Competent Laboratory Teachers

Target Beneficiaries: All Laboratory Teachers in Private Schools of Bacoor City

Duration: 7-hour Free Seminar Training

Conclusions

Based on the salient findings of this study, it revealed that the teachers are competent in the areas of planning and teaching materials, instructional strategies, communication skills, and evaluation tools using the Hyflex platform. There is a significant difference in the perceptions of the students and teachers themselves in their competencies. There is a significant relationship between the competencies of the teachers and their years of experience in the teaching profession, as well as the forms of training attended.

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